

Financial Market and Its Position Today

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Abstract:

This article examines the financial market and ways of its further development, as well as a number of factors that hinder it. In addition, the role of the stock market in the economy, as well as the scientific-theoretical views of foreign and domestic scientists on the financial market and its current role, as well as its further development, were analyzed.

Keywords: stock market, securities, capital, shares, bonds, financial instruments.

Today, it is very important that all necessary conditions are being created for foreign investors to enter the market in Uzbekistan. In addition, he touched on the existing problems related to the trust of citizens. This was due to the difficulty of receiving deposits from the population due to problems related to cash. Today, citizens' deposits are 100 percent protected. Efforts are being made to improve service delivery and protect investors' rights against any fraud and lies. There is no doubt that all the measures taken will have a positive effect on the further development of the capital market. For this, it is necessary to introduce new modern methods that allow the automation of the banking system and increase the efficiency of service provision. Of course, regulating the financial market is a very difficult task. As trends are constantly changing, new trends and products appear that expand the range of financial instruments, and it is precisely because of these factors that we face several obstacles in the development of the financial market.

In the economic literature, there are studies and analyzes of the financial market and its origins, its segments, especially the stock market, and a number of factors hindering its development and their elimination. is presented as a set of market institutions that direct the flow from the saver to the borrower. 1 According to the definition of V.E. Chernova, one of the foreign scientists², the financial market is the total amount of all monetary resources in constant motion, i.e., these are used by various subjects of the economy. is placement and redistribution through changes in demand and supply of resources. From the above analysis, it can be noted that the financial market, with the help of these financial institutions, brings together sectors with a need for funds and those with excess funds. Also, the financial market serves as the main support in the development of the economy,

and by further improving its infrastructure, it is possible to achieve economic stability in the country and increase investment attractiveness.

Research methodology. In this article, the scientific-theoretical views of foreign and domestic scientists on the financial market and its place today, as well as several factors hindering its development and measures to prevent them, were analyzed. Several methods such as assessment, monitoring, analysis, synthesis were used during the research.

Analysis and results.

After a decade of earthquakes following the seismic financial crisis of 2007, the global financial landscape has changed considerably. Foreign direct investment has

fallen by 65 percent since 2007, from \$12.4 trillion to \$4.3 trillion (Figure 1). Half of this decline reflects a sharp decline in cross-border lending and other banking activities. But it is wrong to conclude that financial globalization is over. A new study by the McKinsey Global Institute, *The New Dynamics of Financial Globalization*, concludes that what has emerged from the rubble is a risk-sensitive,

rational, and ultimately more resilient version of global financial integration. Examines the dynamics and factors behind the downsizing of banks in Europe and

the United States, examines changes in global banking and the expansion of foreign operations of banks in other developed and developing economies. It assesses the general state of financial globalization and takes into account the changing roles of countries in the world financial system. It offers a forward-looking view of the global financial system, which promises greater stability, but old and new risks remain will discuss how they can respond to the new era and the new digital technologies that may shape cross-border financial relationships in the future.

Conclusions and suggestions. At the same time, he said that this issue should not be based only on the development of the banking sector, for this it is important to attract investors, create an infrastructure that meets international standards, and gain the trust of not only large market participants, but also the trust of ordinary citizens. Because people have to trust the local market

1Edwin G. Dolan, Coin D.Campbeli , Rosemary G. Campbell. Money, banking and monetary policy. C. "HarcourtSchool", 1988. P. 15.

2Чернова В.Э. Финансовые рынки: учебное пособие/СПбГТУПИ. –СПб.:2015. 73 с

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